

Study of Stability Constants of Complexes of some Divalent Metal Ions and Rare Earth Metal Ions with 5-Benzal-3-phenyl-2-thioxo-4-imidazolidinone

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The stepwise stability constants of complexes of 5-benzal-3-phenyl-2-thioxo-4-imidazolidinone with Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Cd^{2+} as transition metal ions and Sm^{3+} , Gd^{3+} and Dy^{3+} as rare earth metal ions are determined by Calvin-Bjerrum potentiometric titration method. The study was conducted in 3 : 1 (v/v) dioxane-water medium at ionic strength 0.1μ and temperature $27 \pm 1^\circ$. The order of the stability constants is found to be in agreement with the order reported by earlier workers. In case of rare earth metal ions, the stability constants observed are slightly lower as compared to the divalent metal ions studied, thereby indicating lesser ionic character.

STOICHIOMETRIC stability constants of 5-membered ring compounds containing sulphur with different metal ions in solution have been extensively studied. 2-Thioxo-4-imidazolidinone also called 2-thiohydantoin belongs to this class of 5-membered heterocyclic compounds. The determination of stoichiometric stability constants of 2-thioxo-4-imidazolidinone, its 3-*N*-substituted derivatives and 5,5-dimethyl-3-*N*-substituted derivatives have been carried out¹. The present investigation is aimed at determining the stoichiometric stability constant of 5-benzal-3-phenyl-2-thioxo-4-imidazolidinone (1) also called 5-benzal-3-phenyl-2-thiohydantoin with some transition and rare earth metal ions.

N-1 position in the compound is not substituted, thus giving rise to the tautomeric form $\text{N}=\text{C}-\text{SH}$ from where the proton dissociates and the metal ion forms a complex. This is confirmed by ir spectral studies² of 2-thioxo-4-imidazolidinone and its 3-*N*-derivatives which give vibrations, characteristic of SH and C=N in dioxane medium and vibrations characteristic of C=S in KBr matrix.

Experimental

5-Benzal-3-phenyl-2-thioxo-4-imidazolidinone was prepared by standard methods³. The ligand being sparingly soluble in water, a medium of 3 : 1 (v/v) dioxane-water was used. Metal ions used were in the form of metal perchlorates prepared from A. R. grade metal oxides. The concentrations of the metal perchlorate solutions were determined by EDTA titrations. The pH readings were taken on a Phillips PR 950M with glass-calomel electrode assembly at $27 \pm 1^\circ$. Nitrogen atmosphere is maintained throughout the titration. The free acid, free acid plus ligand, free acid plus ligand plus metal ion are titrated separately against

carbonate-free standard sodium hydroxide solution (1.0601 M). Sodium perchlorate was added to maintain constant ionic strength.

Results and Discussion

Due to basic N at 1-position, the protonation takes place, hence the graph of B against volume of alkali added showed back curves in case of acid plus ligand plus metal ion titration. New graphs

Fig. 1.

were obtained by shifting the curves with equivalent amount of alkali for the protons absorbed. \bar{n}_A values were obtained by Irving and Rossotti equations and then pK values for the reagent are calculated. This value was confirmed by the plots of (i) B vs \bar{n}_A and (ii) B vs $\log \bar{n}_A/(1-\bar{n}_A)$ (Fig. 1).

Fig. 2.

Fig. 3.

As per Irving and Rossotti method, \bar{n} values were calculated and plotted against the corresponding calculated pL values to obtain the formation curves of the metal complexation equilibria (Figs. 2 and 3). These formation curves were used to determine $\log k_1$ and $\log k_2$ by half-integral method. In some cases $\log k_2$ values are obtained by extrapolating the graphs. The curves obtained are fairly symmetrical in nature in all the cases. Limits of error and the standard deviation for k values were applied and the most representative values are recorded in Table 1. The order of stability constants in case of divalent transition metal ions studied is found to be $Cu > Cd > Zn \gg Ni$.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF COMPLEXES

Temp. = $27 \pm 1^\circ$, $\mu = 0.1$							
Metal ion	Cu ^{II}	Zn ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cd ^{II}	Sm ^{III}	Gd ^{III}	Dy ^{III}
$\log k_1$	11.025	9.350	5.700	10.000	7.50	8.12	8.40
$\log k_2$	7.40	—	4.425	6.25	—	—	—

The observed order is in agreement with the order given by Irving and Williams. The observed order $Cd > Zn$ is in agreement with the observations made earlier with few exceptions^{4,5}. This order is further supported by the exceptions based on, increase in ionisation potential and reciprocal ionic radius on passing from cadmium to zinc. However, the observed order $Zn > Ni$ contradicts the order $Cu > Ni > Zn$ given by Mellor and Maley⁶ but is supported by many other workers⁷⁻⁹. The reversal of this order is attributed to steric factors.

As regards complexes of rare earth metal ions, the stability constants were slightly lower as compared to the divalent metal ions, thereby indicating lesser ionic character. In order to find the detailed stability order, the study of the whole series of lanthanides is under investigation.

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